

A Conceptual Review of Induction and Orientation on the Job Performance of New Employees in Tertiary Institutions: Delta State University Abraka in Perspective

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Abstract

The paper conceptualized a review of induction and orientation on the job performance of new employees in tertiary institutions with Delta State University, Abraka in perspective. The researchers observed from experience, the induction and orientation programme conducted recently by the Dean, faculty of education, Delta State University, Abraka on the 4th November, 2024 was indeed an effective orientation programme with the aim of knowing newly employed staff responsibilities in the faculty, and how to contribute successfully towards achieving management goals. Moreover, it is a socializing process through which the new employees, transferred, re-categorized and promoted staffs are seen as an avenue to achieve both personal and institutions goals. Induction and orientation as concepts have been defined by various authors based on their ideology. Studies reviewed showed that there is a positive correlation between effective induction and orientation programmes and improved job performance among new employees. Despite the recognized benefits, implementing effective induction and orientation programmes in tertiary institutions presents unique challenges which includes: the wide range of roles, from academic to administrative, requires customized induction content; new employees may have differing levels of prior experience, necessitating a flexible approach to training. limited funding and staffing can hinder the development and delivery of comprehensive programmes etc. The paper is anchored on TPI theory originally propounded by Bloom in 1956, which has been used by several authors to examine the effectiveness and employee's performance in both public and private sectors towards attainment of stipulated goals. This TPI theory is in three categories, namely: theoretical knowledge, practical knowledge and integration towards better performance of job done. The "T" refers to: Theoretical knowledge, "P" refers to: practical knowledge and "I" refers to: integration of both knowledge towards better performance. The paper recommends that management of tertiary institution should give total support towards induction training and mentorship as guide in facilitating the job performances of new employees.

Keywords: Induction, Orientation, Job Performance TPI Theory & New Employees

Introduction

The integration of new employees into an organization is a critical process that significantly influences their subsequent job performance. In tertiary institutions, where the work environment is both complex and multifaceted, effective induction and orientation programs are essential. Oroka and Oroka (2020) opined that established organizational culture affects employee's productivity, performance, commitment, self-confidence, and ethical behaviour. Hence, new employees must be integrated into institutions organizational system through induction and orientation. This review examines the theoretical underpinnings of induction and orientation and their impact on the job performance of new employees in tertiary institutions. An organization or institution that needs to maintain a standard have to provide new employees with necessary business information about their position, the organizational objectives and their responsibilities so as to enable them gain a full view of the business by performing their duties effectively and efficiently. Induction for newly employee is not just welcoming the new hires into the business and showing them the ropes, rather it entails assisting them to gain the required knowledge to achieve the status of valuable assets for the organization or institution.

Stewart and Brown (2019), saw induction training as the planned introduction of new employees to employer's expectations of the jobs that the employees is going to fill through a workforce management solution, the rules of the organization culture such as company policies and contracts, and however what the employee's performance is going to be measured against. Induction training is an inevitable activity because it helps the newly employees, promoted, re-categorized and transferred employees to settle properly and quickly in their new roles and responsibilities. Mchete and Shayo (2020), view induction training as an avenue to communicate the company's vision and values, shape the new employee's values and remove too many unrealistic expectations by stakeholders or professional individuals in the organization.

Orientation is the starting point of future issues that promotes awareness and adaptability through performance of duties and social assimilation. Orientation makes the new employees feel at home, get socialized, equipped with basic information that will enhance performance of official functions effectively. Once a person has accepted a job offer, it's necessary that organization or institution should assist the new, promoted, re-categorized and transferred employees to adapt to the rule and regulations and its policies. Indeed, some organizations or institutions do not conduct induction and orientation program often for new staffs due to the challenges that accomplished it. It is against this background that the researcher decided to stress the implementation of induction training and orientation program despite the challenges. However, orientation as a prerequisite for human resources development is crucial for ensuring a smooth adaptation, knowledge, integrated and well-performing employees as assets toward organizational success. A well-planned induction and orientation process can make a significant difference in promoting engagement and participation, fostering a sense of belonging by reducing anxiety and uncertainty.

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According to Chagelisbvili (2022), orientation show the new employees the organization or institution on a wider scale, understanding its vision for the future, current state and its past. He also commends on different levels in the orientation process such as: level of compliance clarification, culture and connections.

The researchers observed from experience, the induction and orientation programme conducted recently by the Dean, faculty of education, Delta State University, Abraka on the 4th November, 2024 was indeed an effective orientation programme with the aim of knowing newly employed staff responsibilities in the faculty, and how to contribute successfully towards achieving management goals. Moreover, it is a socializing process through which the new employees, transferred, re-categorized and promoted staffs are seen as an avenue to achieve both personal and institutions goals. While organization (Delta State University, Abraka) tries as well as to make the new employees, an agent for the attainment of its stipulated goals and objectives.

To specialize in any skills, there must be a proper implementation of induction and orientation programme on new employees to help effective performance in organizations or institutions like Delta State University. According to Ifovwe et al (2023), employees that are satisfied with the educational system where they work have more experience and better skill for performance in the work place. When induction and orientation is lacking, it could cause misinformation, frustration and employee turnover. Based on this, the researchers reviewed how induction and orientation programs are implemented and its challenges on their job performances of new employees, promoted, transferred, and re-categorized based on their theoretical, practical knowledge, and integration at the organization like Delta State University. Abraka.

Concept of Induction and Orientation

Induction and orientation as concepts have been defined by various authors based on their ideology. It is a planned programme to socialize the new employees, transferred, re-categorized and promoted employees with the co-workers and the school environment. The term induction is coined from Latin word “inducer” which means “to bring or introduce”. Induction is often used interchangeably with orientation. Peretomode (2023) deposed induction as the process of welcoming new employees into an organization and familiarizing them with the employing organization and the work setting. He also revealed that orientation is very essential for existing employees who have been promoted to higher positions or transferred to various units to do their jobs or departments responsibilities, as well as the organization’s policies, rules, objectives and services of the organization or institution.

Smith (2020), defined induction as a process through which organization describe to the new employee the organizational history, structure, fringe, benefits, rules and regulations. On the other part, induction refers to the process of introducing new employees, students or individual to an organization or institution. Smith conducted a study on training approaches and employee’s performance in state corporations, he applied TPI theory to determine the extent in which induction

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and orientation has influence newly employee's ability in carry their responsibilities. He further concluded that new employee performance is based on how they work together as a team and also recommended that organization need to improve in formal training program for all new employees irrespective of the categories in other to enhance well stated procedures for every department of the institution, mostly in public sectors.

According to Hewitt (2002) in his study of the effects of satisfactory orientation training to new employees using the TPI theory. The study revealed that orientation training has been favorable to employees to achieve theoretical and practical knowledge as avenue for them to collaborates learning as a team, expose to technique to do their job and share ideas about past job performance just to improve or adjust on their skills.

Alberta (2012), investigated on the effects of employee's orientation on performance in the Ghana education service at Accra. He revealed that induction training leads to job satisfaction and commitment, acquisition of knowledge and skills, expose to organizational culture, mission and vision and capacity to work through orientation program conducted that enhance job performance.

William (2018), revealed that induction training has positive influence on the service that lecturers provide based on their awareness to the learners. Hence, it is necessary to create an avenue for newly employees to perform their best in an organization or institution.

Challenges Faced by Tertiary Institutions in Induction and Orientation Training Programme

According to Patel et al (2023), despite the recognized benefits, implementing effective induction programmes in tertiary institutions presents unique challenges which includes:

1. **Diverse Job Roles:** The wide range of roles, from academic to administrative, requires customized induction content.
2. **Varied Experience Levels:** New employees may have differing levels of prior experience, necessitating a flexible approach to training.
3. **Resource Constraints:** Limited funding and staffing can hinder the development and delivery of comprehensive programmes.
4. **Complex Organizational Structures:** Navigating the hierarchical and bureaucratic nature of tertiary institutions can be daunting for new employees.

Other challenges include:

- **Lack of support from top management:** This refers to insufficient fund and inadequate budgets from the higher authorities.
- **Insufficient time:** rushing the induction and orientation process can lead new employees with unanswered questions and feeling anxious and unprepared.

- Lack of role clarity: failure to clearly communicate expectations, roles, and responsibilities can lead to confusion and misunderstandings. When your employees don't have a clear understanding of their job role, they tend to get discouraged. So, in a way to prevent this, you need to center your programs on individual employee roles and make them understand their job functions.
- Evaluation and follow-up: measuring the effectiveness of induction and orientation process and collecting feedback from new employees can be challenging. Without proper evaluation mechanisms in place, employees may struggle with ongoing integration and professional development. Lack of the follow-up can lead to unresolved issues and lower job satisfactions.
- Lack of training: the manager who provides the orientation and induction program to the new hires may not be experienced or trained about the methods of orientation or sometimes the manager may not have enough time to orient the new employees.

Impact of Induction and Orientation on Job Performances

Recent studies have demonstrated a positive correlation between effective induction programs and improved job performance among new employees. For instance, induction training at the U N Mehta Institute of Cardiology & Research Centre in 2021 significantly enhanced employees' knowledge of their rights, responsibilities, and clinical practices, leading to better performance (Patel et al., 2023). Similarly, research conducted at the Open University of Tanzania highlighted that induction training is crucial in enhancing the performance of new employees by providing essential theoretical and practical knowledge, as well as facilitating their integration into the workplace (Mchete & Shayo, 2020).

Studies underscore that well-structured orientation programmes can reduce turnover rates and improve employee morale. Also, supportive and strong institutional cultural operations can stimulate an average employee to perform brilliantly whereas a negative and weak culture may demotivate an outstanding employee to underperform (Oroka and Oroka, 2020). These programmes provide new employees with a clearer understanding of their roles, expectations, and organizational culture, contributing to a more positive workplace experience. In the academic context, induction programs tailored to address pedagogical methodologies and research expectations have been shown to improve the quality of teaching and research output (Klein & Weaver, 2000). In summary, well-designed induction programs not only enhance job performance by equipping new employees with the necessary knowledge and skills but also foster a supportive work environment that can lead to higher employee satisfaction and retention.

Theoretical Framework

The paper is anchored on TPI theory originally propounded by Bloom in 1956, which has been used by several authors to examine the effectiveness and employee's performance in both public and private sectors towards attainment of stipulated goals. This TPI theory is in three categories, namely: theoretical knowledge, practical knowledge and integration towards better performance of job done. The "T" refers to: Theoretical knowledge, "P" refers to: practical knowledge and "I" refers to: integration of both knowledge towards better performance. This theory revealed the interrelatedness between the study variables, such as newly employees collaborating through knowledge acquired from induction and orientation training and implementation of such knowledge by carrying out their duties efficiently despite the challenges (Bauer and Erdogan, 2011).

Based on the theory of this review, it is obvious that induction and orientation programme is systematic because it highly enhances staff effectiveness at workplace and improve performance. It has also helped them to know their responsibilities and benefits attached to every given task through the theoretical understanding while practical knowledge has helped them to gain mentorship as well as being expressed to new equipment or tools needed to facilitate the job standard. This study reveals information on how induction and orientation help to collaborate learning by integrating both ideals, get specialized, feel belonging with the management staff towards a stipulated goal.

Irrespective of the challenges facing induction and orientation program, such as insufficient time giving to much information at time, lack of role clarity, education and follow-up and lack of training. It shall not be carried out just in a day or few days carelessly rather it should be a continues until the new employees are granded with the process and procedure to achieve management objectives and their personal goals as well this should be so until the individual is fully adapted at least time through a session for an effective performance. However, the paper supports focusing on comprehensive induction and orientation programmes, in order to eradicate the challenges through effective performance of the newly employees with the help of mentorship toward organization of management goals and employee's satisfaction.

Conclusion

Induction and orientation on newly employee's performance at tertiary institution explores the essential implementation of theoretical knowledge, practical knowledge and integration theory adopt to revealed the challenges faced by induction training program and profound solution such as focusing on continuous orientation till employees adaptivity. Is necessary for every management to implement induction and orientation exercise in order to enable the employees to be abreast in their obligation and be informed about the rules and regulation obtainable in the tertiary institution, since effective induction and orientation also helps employees to feel belongings and boost

productivity in a team work, thereby making them build confidence in exercising their competency and skills at workplace

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made in this review, to engender effective induction and orientation programmes in tertiary institutions:

1. Tertiary institutions management should incorporate theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and social integration components to address all aspects of the TPI theory. Also, the induction content should be tailored to specific roles and departments to ensure relevance and effectiveness.
2. Tertiary institution should develop comprehensive orientation that involves total supports from the management and also, it should entail training and mentorship guide towards performance.
3. Management should allocate sufficient fund to organize induction and orientation programme so as to enable the employees learn in details.
4. Educational organization should evaluate and tender feedback as a means to recognize the usefulness of implementation induction and orientation programme in facilitating employee's performance, job satisfaction and self-actualization.
5. There should be regular assess, review and update on induction and orientation programmes based on feedback and changing organizational or institutional needs and goals.

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